

LEADERSHIP STYLE: A KEY TO RAPID GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT IN ORGANIZATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores a leadership style that is all embracing, free of rancor and misgiving. The growth of every establishment is sacrosanct to the minds of leaders. One major challenge that leaders in Nigeria and some parts of Africa face in its developmental struggle is "leadership". This has led to failures and disregard for subordinates. These challenges are however not farfetched, as the style adopted by leaders either mar or make their establishments. The developmental growth of any sector is attributed to good leadership (style). Being a good leader is like conducting a symphony: You don't necessarily know how to play each instrument but you do know how to make the instruments work together to produce music. Accordingly, three main leadership styles were identified in the study. Success depends upon a number of variables, including the style adopted by the leaders which invariably leads to building better qualities of the following and aspects of the situation. The paper then submits that the democratic style leadership is most effective as it brings about effective leadership qualities in establishment.

Key Words: *Leadership, Style, Growth, Development.*

INTRODUCTION

Roles in organizations involve more than just leadership. It is useful, not yet common in our literature and discussion of business, to distinguish among leadership, management, and administration. They are in fact very different; each is valuable and has its place. Briefly, leadership is about a vision of the future and the ability to energize others to pursue it. Management is about getting result and doing so efficiently so that a financial profit or surplus is created. Administration is about rules and procedures and whether or not they are being followed. These distinctions are very important to clear communications among us, about how organizations are run. Briefly, running an organisation effectively involves: leadership: *vision, energizing*; management: *efficiency, results*, administration: *rules, procedures*. [www.leadership.com].

Our focus on this paper is on leadership style - how an Executive set direction and energizes his organization to pursue the direction. This is appropriate because managerial techniques are being spread fast by imitation, and acquisition of Masters in Business Administration (MBA) education. Administration techniques were generalized around the world decades ago. So what is much different now is leadership. Offiong wrote that some of the major challenges faced by management during the early years of industrial revolution were the development of some scientific principles for handling men, material, money and machinery. This challenge he said took two forms, these were: (i) how to increase productivity of workers, and (ii) how to motivate the workers to take advantage of the new methods and techniques of production of goods and services which was prevalent during the era of industrial revolution [Offiong, 2004: 14].

If there is anything that Nigerians of all walks of life are unanimous about, it is the fact that Nigeria has a stunted growth. Countries such as Malaysia and Indonesia, and many others that were at the same developmental level with her in the 60s during the peak of the decolonization process, have since gone far ahead on the human, material and infrastructural development scales. In contrast, Nigeria, the most populous black nation in the world, appears to be on a steady decline and decay. Leadership style plays a key role in uplifting any human society or holding down the wheel of progress. It is the foundation that determines progress or the absence of it. The ideological/philosophical basis and the manifestations of dominant leadership style in Nigeria is all about the wellbeing of the leaders and their cronies and the entrenchment of their rules by hook or by crook means. Their misrule is also manifested in the spate of onslaughts against perceived opponents. While in the process, the interest and wellbeing of the society are undermined or even ignored. This ought not to be so as the purpose of leadership is about the wellbeing of

the society. It was on the basis of this that Onasanya wrote that leadership is the ability to handle people in a manner that commands confidence, respect and loyalty as well as support the politics of the organization. He added that the leader ought to learn much about human nature, respect the dignity of the individual worker and understand that everyone is as important as himself [Onasanya, 1999: 180].

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Leadership: Leadership brings about the effective discharge of duties and control of human and material resources. It is also about listening, involving and delegating, commitment to employees and consistency. In other words leaders should involve others; delegate duties and show commitment to employees or their subordinate. Accordingly leadership is based on belief that great leaders are made, not born. The behaviour of man in the workplace focuses on actions Of leaders not on mental qualities or internal states. People can learn to become leaders through teaching and observation.

Style: Style deals with the aspect of character trait in leadership. Style culminates to qualitative output in societal development and respect for each order.

Approaches: There are a number of different approaches, or 'styles' to leadership that are based on different assumptions and theories. The style that individuals use will be based on a combination of their beliefs, values and preferences, as well as the organizational culture and norms which will encourage some styles and discourage others. The assumption here refers to a situation where persons' involvement in decision-making improves the understanding of the issues involved by those who must carry out the decisions.

It is therefore imperative that leaders coordinates or direct affairs sincerely as they are also responsible for putting to check excesses by subordinates.

Measures adopted by some leaders in the discharge of their duties gave rise to this research work, which is geared towards the enhancement of leaders in the adoptions of styles capable of projecting the establishment and encouraging subordinates to put in their best in the discharge of their duties.

This paper adopts an eclectic approach propounded by Lewin. These involved the contingency approach; motivational approach; behavioral approach; and participative approach.

Contingency approach: The contingency approach in this paper focuses on particular variables related to the environment that might determine which particular style of leadership is

best suited for the situation, as not all leadership style is best in all situations. Hence, leaders adopt the style best suited for the environment. The contingency approach was referenced to, in order to address the seeming domineering environment where the abilities or leadership skills of a leader is put to test. Such a leader could assume any of the leadership style. Therefore the authoritarian style should normally only be used on rare occasions. More often than not, the contingency approach creates an environment for the following: i) where new, untrained employees who do not know which task to perform or which procedures to follow are given instruction or direction; ii) effective supervision, which can be provided only through detailed order and instructions; iii) employees may not respond to any other leadership style; iv) when high volume of production needs are on a daily basis; v) limited time in which to make decision; vi) when a managers' power is challenged by an employee; vii) when areas are poorly managed; and viii) when work need to be coordinated with another department or organization [Janis, 1982].

Motivation approach: Motivation is said to be the driving force by which humans achieve their goals. Human motivation is rooted in a basic need to minimize physical pain and maximize pleasure, or it may include specific needs such as eating and resting, or a desired object, goal, state of being, ideal, or it may be attributed to less-apparent reasons such as altruism, selfishness, morality, or avoiding mortality [www.wikipedia]. The motivational theory creates an enabling environment for the leaders and subordinates to gain from their efforts without prejudice or fear of failure. This approach talks about how persons are motivated financially or otherwise for smooth operation. However, only few reach all their potentials-even when they are motivated. [Nyenka, 2005].

Behavioral approach: The behavioral theory adopts the belief that great leaders are made, not born. This leadership theory focuses on the actions of leaders and the subordinates not on mental qualities or internal states. According to this theory people can learn to become leaders through teaching and observation. Often times the action of a leader could lead to doom or boom. The character trait to adopt a technique where subordinates' interests are treated fairly and justly leads to motivation and encouragement, as shown in this work which observed that good character trait leads to innovation and commitment. This behaviorism focus is on the attitude of leaders as it goes a long way in affecting the running of the establishment.

Participative approach: The participative approach adopted in this research work promoted the democratic style of leadership which encourages group participation to share ideas and opinions, though the leader retains the final say over decisions. More so, members of the group feel more engaged in the process, as creativity makes them more likely to care for the end results. The research also revealed that democratic leadership leads to higher productivity among group members.

Often, however, as it is within the managers' whim to give or deny control of his or her subordinates, most participative activity is within the immediate team. The question of how much influence others are given thus may vary on the manager's preferences and beliefs, and a whole spectrum of participation is possible, as in the table below.

<i>Non- Participative</i>	<i>Participative/Democratic</i>
Leader proposes decision, listens to feedback, then decides	Joint decision with team as
Rely on threats and punishment to influence employees	Full delegation of decision to
Do not trust employees	Develops plan to help employee evaluate their own performance
Do not allow for employee input	Allows employee to establish
No need to keep employees informed on matter that affects them	Encourages employees to grow the job and be
Do not want employees to share in decision-making and problem-solving duties.	Recognizes and encourage achievement.
Do not encourage employees to develop a high sense of personal growth and job satisfaction	Team proposes decision, leader final

The **autocratic leadership style** is probably the original type of management style ever employed. Simple at heart, the autocratic style of management involves making the decisions yourself and passing them onto subordinates. In the autocratic world, leaders are there to make the decision, and followers are there to follow. This promotes an 'obedient' style of follower present in the army, and perhaps some of the 'tougher' working cultures such as farming, logging, haulage and fishing.

The **democratic leadership style** was probably the most popular leadership style since the beginning of the 21 st century management arena. It's a style that remains popular due to the positive reaction employees have towards it. If you lean towards the democratic leadership style, you seek to consult your employees or team members over decisions that will affect them. Naturally, followers prefer this strategy for several reasons. Either their self-interest attracts

them towards managers that allow them to make the choices that benefit them, or it's euphoric confidence bounce they experience when they're allowed to make decisions that were previously 'above' them.

PROBLEMS OF LEADERSHIP

Some of the problems militating against developmental growth in an establishment, amongst others are as follows:

- Poor listening on the part of leaders;
- Lack of managerial techniques;
- Lack of fair hearing by leaders to resolve welfare or staffing issues in an establishment;
- Lack of support for human development in an establishment;
- Lack of good human relations between leaders and the led;
- Pre-mature judgment by leaders;
- Lack of motivation on the part of leaders to subordinates;
- None adoption of democratic style of leadership;
- The reliability on threat and punishment to influence employee;
- Lack of trust as it relates to subordinates;
- Restricting or hoarding information concerning subordinates;
- Restricting subordinates from decision-making process and problems solving; and
- Lack of recognition and encouragement of subordinates, on achievements by leaders. etc

The above enumerated problems will not hinder the growth or development of an establishment if the leaders adopt democratic or participatory style of leadership. In addition, leaders have the time and want to gain more commitment and motivation from the employees, when he/she adopt the participative style. Group members feel engaged in the process and are more motivated and creative [Lewin & John, 1986:5]. More so the participative Leader, rather than taking autocratic decisions, seeks to involve other people in the process, possibly including subordinates, peers, superiors and other stakeholders. People are more committed to actions where they are involved in the relevant decision-making and are less competitive and more collaborative when they are working on joint goals. When people make decisions together, the social commitment to one another is greater and thus increases their commitment to the decision. Several people deciding together make better decisions than one person alone.

There is no gain saying the fact that hard-work pays with skilful effort. Most successful

businessmen and women try hard to be guided by this principle. That is why leadership is certainly not by intimidation or harassment but by the ability to control fairly but with firmness [Adedeji, 1972:32-36]. The management of human resources is a difficult task, no matter how a person or leader may try, he cannot satisfy everyone. Decisions by leaders have one way or the other affected the populace either negatively or positively. Adoption of control mechanism in a stylish or humane manner had brought succor to subordinates. This has gone a long way to establish goal formations that keeps the organization in the forefront. The systemic and quality style adopted by the leader, put to check negligence, misconduct and abandonment of duty by personnel, as they adhere strictly, to contractual terms and utilize their skills to the development and growth of the organization.

Poor listening has in no small way affected the progress of most establishments. This had caused distortion and communication gap between the workers and their leaders, as it has also led to pre-mature judgment on the part of leaders who adopted the no humane approach. Often times, we have heard of leaders who tend to project the future of their organization and had succeeded in meeting such projections. Adequate atmosphere for different individuals or co-operate bodies to brainstorm on ways to move an organization forward are created their-by bridging the communication gap between leaders and the led. There is no gainsaying the fact that democratic or participative style of leadership seems to be the best option to promote good administrative governance in an establishment.

Experience has shown that leadership is critical. It is competence, it could be accomplishment but if a leader does not understand leadership, he is unable to inspire his team to achieve. He will have many problems which will lead to the inability to succeed in the running of the organization and appreciating the efforts of subordinates. Olaopa posited that "Leadership helps an establishment to develop a shared vision and a unity of purpose. He added that, It is central to building teams and networks, thereby forging the all-important trust that builds an organization, and ensuring that the corporation has the skills to meet the mission. [Olaopa, 2008:80).

It was with regard to these that [Onasanya, 1999:217], on writing on human relations, asserted that "when hostilities, resentments, suspicions and fears of workers are replaced by favourable attitudes, a substantial increase in production occurs. The practice of good human relations does not however mean the creation of a country club to cater for every sentimental

whim and social desire of employees. It is concerned with the establishment of principles and practices that motivate employees to perform their duties to the best of their abilities. The important thing to note here is that treating people like human beings is to make them feel that they are members of the team. Onasanya added that a prompt and fair hearing of workers' complaints, good communication and joint consultation all lead to good human relations which cause employees to find satisfaction and pleasure in performing their assignments and motivates them towards higher achievements.

The failure of some leaders has been traced to the style they adopted, as they tend to ignore the participation of others in the day-to-day running and decision making of the organization. When workers are aggrieved, the smooth running of any establishment is hampered. An aggressive leader initiates a series of bold moves that begin by bringing him much power. Slowly, however, his power reaches a peak, and soon everything turns against him. [Green, 2000:64].

The involvement of all manner of persons in an establishment to form a common front, which, is progress oriented is known as participative style of leadership, while style is substantive in engaging power. There is need to care about the way something is done. In fact the *way* something is done changes the nature of *what* is done.

The style adopted in the process of carrying out instruction in leadership leads to positive outcome. There should amongst others be; accountability, good character display, effective communication, trust, team work, openness, etc, these has great influence on confidence building in the leadership. These also led to cordial relationship between management and workers, as it creates room for the initiation of positive ideas, build corporate character, and bring to bear leadership qualities that breed unity and promote the participative or democratic style of leadership.

DIFFERENT LEADERSHIP STYLE

Amongst the leadership styles propounded by Lewin (1939), three styles were chosen for comparison in this write-up, these are:

- a. **Autocratic Leadership:** Authoritarian leaders, also known as autocratic leaders, provide clear expectations for what needs to be done, when it should be done, and how it should be done.

There is also a clear division between the leaders and the followers. Authoritarian leaders make

decisions independently with little or no input from the rest of the group. Offiong posited that the authoritarian leaders believe that subordinates lack creativity and sense of responsibility, and so management must provide very close supervision [1997: 13 1]. While Okoh asserted that the style is more useful in the military and one-man business organizations [2005:358]. Researchers also found that decision-making was less creative under authoritarian leadership. The style is usually viewed as controlling, bossy, and dictatorial. Authoritarian leadership is best applied to situations where there is little time for group decision-making or where the leader is the most knowledgeable member of the group.

- b. **Participative Leadership:** Lewin's study found that participative leadership, also known as democratic leadership, was generally the most effective leadership style. Democratic leaders offer guidance to group members, but they also participate in the group and allow input from other group members. In Lewin's study, people in this group were more productive than the members of the authoritarian group, but their contributions were of a much higher quality. Perhaps this was what Onasanya wrote that, the people are responsible adults who will discipline themselves so long as they are treated reasonably [1999: 181]. More participative leaders encourage group members to participate, but retain the final say over the decision-making process. Group members feel encouraged in the process and are motivated and creative.

- c. **Delegative (Laissez-Faire) Leadership:** Researchers found that people under the delegative leadership, also known as laissez-faire leadership, were the least productive of all three groups. The people in this group also made more demands on the leader, showed little cooperation and were unable to work independently. Delegative leaders offer little or no guidance to group members and leave decision-making up to group members [Okoh, 2005:359]. While this style can be effective in situation where group members are highly qualified in an area of expertise, it often leads to poorly defined roles and a lack motivation [Lewin, K., Lipsett, R. and White, R.K., 1939:IO,271-301].

ADVANCING THE DEMOCRATIC STYLE OF LEADERSHIP

From the above analysis it is obvious why the participative or democratic style of leadership was most preferred by the author, as it breeds cooperation and cordiality on the one hand and adds values and guidance on the other hand. In addition, using the participative style with a team of workers who know their job. The leader tends to know the problem, but does not have all the information. The employees know their jobs and want to become part of the team and solution to the problem.

Some leaders deviate from the participative style of leadership, thereby hampering development and growth of the establishment. Some leaders still believe in the old ways of discharging duties as they believe that the people are tools to be used and dumped at will. This could be the reason why Tonwe in referencing Mary Parker Follet posited that, the old ideas of leadership are changing because of the changes in the concept of human relations and developments in management. He added that a leader is not the president organization or head of the department and that a leader is the man who can energize his group, who knows how to encourage initiative, and how to draw from all what each has to give and that the leader not only influences the group, but also influenced it [Tonwe, 2004: 162-163].

Furthermore, distrust and bias in management is usually removed, when a leader treats his people democratically. It affords the people an opportunity for increased knowledge, which could be applied to increased productivity and production of goods and services, in the process contributing concretely to economic development and higher quality of life for the citizen [Osagie, 2009:110].

Democratic approach to leadership has indeed allow subordinates to work more productively as the leaders let them know that the work they are doing or their contributions to the establishment is worth-while and important. Inspirations like these from leaders culminate in the enthusiastic workability of the workers towards achieving set-out goals. Of course a polite rebuke and correction over poor job performance could also be useful. The worker accepts his mistake and takes subsequent correction(s) in good faith. Okoh noted that "there is a need for recognition, security and sense of belonging in determining a worker's morale and productivity more than the physical conditions in which he works". Workers can be creative and direct themselves properly if well motivated. The existence of leader in any establishment is to effectively control, direct and

guide subordinates towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. This was why Okoh related it to the objective of harmony in the establishment. [Okoh, 2005:345-367].

Moreso Onasanya added that, "unsatisfactory human relations and unfavorable attitudes exert an appreciable restraining influence on production because they are dissatisfiers which, demotivates workers" [Onasanya, 1999: 181].

Notwithstanding, highly successful leaders are at risk for developing *huris* (hobbies), which in turn lead to failure of varying degrees. History has shown that some leaders make disastrous decision. I believe that one of the most important thing, a leader can do when he/she needs to make an important decision, is to "decide *how to decide*."

Democratic (Participative) style of leadership amongst others, promote: (i) prompt payment of workers wages or salaries; (ii) knowledge driven in subordinates; (iii) encourages innovative ideas amongst workers; and (iv) amicable resolution of grievances amongst workers.

- a. **Prompt Payment of workers' Wages or Salaries:** Wages are the rewards paid to workers for supplying their labour and services to an enterprise [Helson, 2001 :294]. Onasanya added that wages are usually referred to the compensation paid to manual workers or operatives and generally to factory workers below the supervisory- grade whereas salary is paid to office workers (white collar jobs) or to the supervisors of the wage earners. [Onasanya, 1999:133].

There is no gainsaying the fact that prompt payment of workers entitlement encourages the workers to achieve set aims and objectives. Leadership is less about your needs, and more about the need of the people, and the organization you are leading. Leadership styles are not something to be tried on like so many suits, to see which fits. Rather, they should be adapted to the particular demands of the situation, the particular requirements of the people involved and the particular challenges facing the organization. Thus ensuring that workers are paid as at when due. Management therefore must be proactive in this regard as none or delay payments are usually viewed by the workers as denial and insensitivity on the part of management, as emotion cloud reason, and if management cannot see the situation clearly, they cannot prepare for and respond to it with any degree of control. Anger is the most destructive responses for it will cloud the workers vision the most. A hungry man is an angry man.

b. **Knowledge Driven In subordinates:** The acquisition of training helps workers to build proficiency and provide them with the opportunity to represent their establishment in any given opportunity. Training of workers has become synonymous with success. In every sector of the economy, persons of proven integrity and with professional and intellectual background are recommended to serve. According to Socrates a Greek philosopher, he observed that; " ... the purpose of knowledge is to enable man live a good life, for knowledge is a means to a moral way of life. He declared that there was need to persuade everyone to look into himself and seek virtue before seeking his private interests" [Omoregbe,1993: 158]. It is therefore pertinent to note that the selection of workers for training periodically or as the case may be is necessary for the developmental growth of an establishment and the individuals. Taylor believed that, it is the responsibility of the management to develop or train the workers and offer them opportunities for advancement so that, they can do the job to the fullest realization of their natural capacities. He added that the employees should accept the new methods, tools and conditions willingly and enthusiastically. [Tonwe, 2004:60].

The effective development of the human resources of an enterprise is one of the most vital contributions to the future and long-term growth of development and survival of any establishment. Henry Lawrence Gantt wrote that "workers should be trained in the habit of industry and co-operation", in his modified paper presented in 1908. He said that systematic training in habits of industry is an effective system of cooperation between workmen and foremen, as it is a faster method to produce not only the work but, better quality work, with fewer mistakes and less scrap. This he said is due to the increased attention and concentration given [Tonwe, 2004:60-76].

Moreso, leadership is visionary. The power of training is to modify, motivate, educate and improve the quality of human resources. Jobs must be assigned to fit people with all their strength and weakness and people must be encouraged to contribute effectively to organizational goals [Okoh, 2004:380- 386]. Thus, the style of leadership presupposes that all employees, irrespective of their positions, must be trained not only to be good on their jobs, but also to know the facts about the enterprise that employs them. They should be trained to be ambassadors of goodwill for the enterprise [Adebayo, 2008:24]. Refreshers course also has a way of improving the knowledge, skills and attitudes of the employees in the performance of their jobs [icolson, 1969]. Leaders should know they are ultimately responsible for the lives and fortunes of people. [Umoh, 2000:111-127].

- c. **Encourages Innovative Ideas amongst workers:** The style of leadership introduced in any sector culminates into the creation of innovative ideas. Some persons in an establishment might have wonderful ideas, skills or talent to contribute towards the establishment, but because of lack of encouragement and style of leadership in place, such a person might be unwilling to reveal these ideas, But under a democratically leadership such a person will share ideas with management freely, without fear of molestation or intimidation, While the introduction of this new idea or acquired skills by subordinates leads to "innovation".

An Innovation is a new idea, which may be a recombination of old ideas, a scheme that challenges the present order, a formula, or a unique approach which is perceived as new by the individual involved [Zaltman, 1973]. Included in this definition are both technical innovations (new technologies, products and services) and administrative innovations (new procedures, policies and organizational forms). Daft and Becker (1978) and others have emphasized keeping technical and administrative innovations distinct. Ruttan and Hayami (1984:203) have shown that many technological innovations in agriculture and elsewhere could not have occurred without innovations in institutional and organizational arrangements. Learning to understand the close connection between technical and administrative dimensions of innovations is a key part of understanding leadership. In view of these leaders tends to share ideas with workers and workers also do same. Based on the newly acquired skills, the organization is better positioned to tackle issue(s) that may arise. Adebayo (2008: 160) said that "experience gained is no doubt a very good training in the making of an administrator".

Steps taken to improve innovative idea of personnel is not a wasted effort, as performance will come to nothing if there is no adequate training provided for those who will function as managers. In a nutshell, progress is hampered in most establishments due to lack of managerial performance. The application of democratic style in the management of affairs by leaders tends to lead to positive charge which is geared towards the steady growth of the establishment. Change is an ever-present feature in the management of an establishment. It was with regards to these that Olaopa (2008:93-94) wrote that, change falls into three categories: which are - "essentially internal change driven by continuous improvement or strategic initiative in an effort to improve service and reduce costs; externally driven change in which the organization can strategically determine how to respond; and environmental change, driven externally by the effect of technology and globalization".

Furthermore, Kimberly wrote that, innovation is often viewed as a good thing because the new

idea must be useful-profitable, constructive, or solve a problem [March, 1981]. New ideas that are not perceived as useful are not normally called innovations, they are usually called mistakes. Objectively, of course, the usefulness of an idea can only be determined after the innovation process is completed and implemented. Moreover, while many new ideas are proposed in organizations, only a very few receive serious consideration and developmental effort [Wilson, 1996]. People become attached to ideas over time through a social-political process of putting their ideas into good use. Thus leadership style becomes a veritable tool used for the rejuvenation of an establishment [Oronsaye, 1997: 129-143].

- d. **Amicable Resolution of Grievances:** The effective discharge of duties that led to the attainment of set-out goals is as a result of the effective management of complaint and grievances by leaders. Democratic style of leadership plays a fundamental role in this regard. Okoh posited that, any employer who employs and work with people must have problems, no matter the favorable climate of the industrial relations. These problems he said could be in form of unfair treatment or likely reactions to change [2005:311-315]. The amicable settlement of grievances amongst subordinates can not be overemphasized. It was with regard to this, that Okoh advised that there is need to get to the root cause of any problem(s) and at the same time, provide a fair and speedy settlement of the grievances before it escalates [2005:312]. There is an ample need for leaders to foresee the future of their establishment and take necessary steps to avoid a situation whereby some persons may want to thwart their effort in the establishment of a new height. Experience has rightly shown that the adverse effect is often times unpleasant. Some people are willing to go to any length to prove a point especially when they are disgruntled or aggrieved. Nelson Mandela the former president of South Africa reacted in his 1953 speech, well before his imprisonment that "there is no easy walk to freedom anywhere, and many will have to pass through the valley of the shadow of death again and again before they reach the mountain tops of their desire" [Vijay, 2006: 128]. This is why the democratic style of leadership should be supported and encouraged for organizational development and growth.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Leadership style takes into consideration the value of the need to motivate workers which cannot be fully appreciated until we understand "the worker's notion about work, the attitude of the worker to work and the value the worker places on work" [Leavitt, 1965]. In addition, we have to realize that since the entrepreneur expects a yield or returns on his investments, management has to do everything possible to

encourage the worker to put in his best in order that the expected return is made possible.

There are three major group of leaders mentioned in this write-up, these are: (i) **autocratic leader** - one who makes decision all alone and enforces them by the use of reward and the fear of punishment. This isn't to say that an autocratic leader would fail miserably. The more workers are left to do imaginative or creative tasks largely on their own, the less likely an autocratic leadership style would really 'bring the best' out of the average worker [Lewin, and John: 1986]. (ii) **democratic leader** - one who takes into consideration the wishes and suggestions of the members/followers as well as those of the leader. (iii) **Delegative (Laissez-Faire) Leadership**: Leaders in this category delegate duties and show little cooperation towards achievement of set out goals. Failure is usually blamed on the workers.

Succinctly, some of the problems being faced by leaders in their lack of participation with subordinates includes: poor listening; lack of managerial techniques; lack of fair hearing to resolve welfare or staffing issues; lack of support for human development; lack of good human relations, pre-mature judgment; lack of motivation; the reliability on threat and punishment to influence employee; lack of trust; restricting or hording information concerning subordinates; restricting subordinates from decision-making process and problems solving; and, lack of recognition and encouragement. These problems can be resolved and taken care off easily, by the simple application of democratic style of leadership, as avenues for resolution are created through democratic means by leaders. The creation of these avenues provides security and peaceful co-existence amongst leaders and subordinates. However, the level of participation may also depend on the type of decision being made. Decisions on how to implement goals may be highly participative, whilst decisions during subordinate performance evaluations are more likely to be taken by the Manager. Lack of up- to-date rules can cause delays, ineffectiveness and inefficiency as they can occasion wastage. [Irnhanlahimhin, 2000:247].

However, the democratic leadership style isn't perfect in every occasion. Democratic decisions aren't perfect, in the sense that they take longer to make. When one only has to consult oneself, a decision can be made almost instantaneously. In a war-time, life-threatening or high-risk situation, 'democratic' debate simply isn't relevant. It simply isn't optimal. Examples of these high pressure decision-making jobs include surgeons, army generals, fire-marshals and air traffic controllers. The democratic process is used best in simple manufacturing sectors, where a respite from the harsh and 'robotic' leadership styles recommended by Ford or

other factory managers of times gone by [Zaltrnan, 1973].

Conclusively the style of leadership does not guarantee likeliness of results nor even peace. We will continue to have to work for economic progress and peace, it will not come automatically. Leaders who move up have greater freedom to control their destinies, but also increased pressure and seduction. Leadership style as we have said brings about ways things are done. The differences in styles most markedly reflect the stage of development of an establishment and the economy in general. Leadership in this sense becomes innovative, hard driving, very flexible, ambitious, optimistic, visionary in the technology and business aspects, it plays a good but not dominant role.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Amongst the three styles of leadership enumerated in this work, i.e. *autocratic*, *participative and delegative* styles, it is believed that the participative style of leadership is most appropriate in dealing with workers. This is so in view of the fact that it involves close teamwork with others. In Europe for example, this style of leadership is most effective and acceptable. Leadership style if properly adopted creates a whole system devoid of rancor and failure.

Leadership

is about getting things done for the establishment and influencing people by providing purpose, direction, and motivation, while operating to accomplish the mission and improving the organization. The means of getting people to do what you want them to do is a means of achieving two ends that is, operating and improving, using the participative style with a team of workers who knows their job. The worker's notion of work can be described as any understanding by a human being involving mental and also physical efforts for the reward to keep body and soul together [Leavitt, 1965]. It is therefore an input by a human being in a clear understanding that he would be materially compensated sufficiently to enable him and his dependent continues to exist in reasonable comfort.

Finally, it is therefore recommended that the democratic (participative) style of leadership is best in organizational growth and development. This is so because it is supportive, friendly, helpful, fair, but firm and serving the interest of subordinates as well as those of the organization. It also helps leaders to trust and build confidence in the ability of workers and, initiate positive integration and motivation of subordinates as there is high expectation of performance and adequate training. Provision of special coaching for subordinates to enhance their creativity,

initiative and total job performance is gained through a democratic approach. The worker appreciate those who pilot the affairs of the organization, as they strive to ensure that all hands are on deck to promote tolerance, peaceful co-existence and progress in their various fields of endeavour. By appreciation the workers themselves began to learn and observe the workability of those who direct the affairs of the establishment. Moreso, this style of leadership put to check negligence, misconduct and abandonment of duty by personnel. As they adhere strictly to contractual terms and utilize their skills to the growth of the establishment.

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